

Factors For The Development Of Innovative Thinking Of Students Of Military Education Faculties

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Abstract: *This article contains thoughts and opinions about the factors of development of innovative thinking of students of military education faculties and modern teaching methods - interactive methods, role and importance of innovative technologies.*

Keywords — science, pedagogue, student, method, innovation, education, technology, social-psychological, scientific-technical.

INTRODUCTION.

President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.M.In Mirziyoyev's address to the Supreme Assembly, "as long as we set ourselves the ultimate goal of establishing the foundation of the third renaissance in our country, for this we must create environments and conditions that educate the new Khwarazmians, Berunians, Ibn Sina, Ulughbek, Nawab and Babur. In this, first of all, the development of education and upbringing, the decision-making of a healthy lifestyle, the advancement of Science and innovation should serve as the main pillars of our national idea"[1], he emphasizes.

In order to solve the problems before the educational system in the innovative processes taking place in our country, in the military sphere, as in all areas, it is necessary to be able to assimilate new information and evaluate the acquired knowledge by themselves, to make the necessary decisions, to be independent and free-minded. Therefore, the role and importance of modern teaching methods-interactive methods, innovative technologies - in the educational and educational process of educational institutions is incomparable.[2]

The knowledge of pedagogical technology and their application in education, the experience ensures that students have an educated and mature qualification. Innovative education (Eng. "innovation" – innovation, invention) - education that creates the opportunity for the formation of a new idea in the educational institution, the formation of rules, advanced ideas created by other individuals, qualities related to the natural adoption of rules, qualifications. [2]

Educational innovation is also known as "innovative education". The concept of "innovative education" was first applied in 1979 in the club of Rome.[3]

According to the "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan", innovation has the following content and concepts: "innovation (Eng. "innovations" – introduced innovation, invention)-1) funds spent on the economy to ensure the replacement of generations of technology and Technology; 2) innovations in such fields as Technology, Technology, Management and labor organization based on scientific and technological achievements and advanced experience, as well as their application in various fields and spheres of activity".[4]

A.I. According to Prigozhin, innovation should be understood as a new approach to the attitude towards a certain social unit – organization, population, society, group-in accordance with the goal, enriching this attitude with somewhat stagnant elements. In this regard, it is understood that the author's views directly express the essence of social relations, an innovative approach to them. It follows that each person, as a citizen, specialist, leader, employee, moreover, as a participant in the process of various social relations, organizes a kind of innovative activity.[5]

American psychologist E. Rodgers studied in his research the socio-psychological aspects of social relations with an innovative character, the introduction of innovations in social relations, the categories of persons involved in this process, their relationship to innovation, the degree of acceptance of innovation, readiness to realize the essence, and the classification of social relations with an innovative character between certain categories of individuals. Technologies used in the process of innovative education are known as innovative educational technologies or educational innovations.[6]

Educational innovation-a form, method and technology that can guarantee a much more effective result than before, applied in the field of education or in the educational process with the aim of solving the existing problem on the basis of a new approach.

Innovations look different. The following are considered the main manifestations of innovation: new ideas; specific goals aimed at assimilating the system or direction of activity; unconventional approaches; unusual initiatives; advanced work methods.[7]

One of the important aspects inherent in modern education is the achievement of the profession of an innovative character of pedagogical activity. The issue of achieving the profession of an innovative character of pedagogical activity in developed foreign countries has begun to be seriously studied since the 60s of the last century.[8]

In Particular, V.I. Zagvyazinsky, V.A. KanKalik, V.A. In the work carried out by researchers such as Slastenin[7;8;9;10], the content of practical actions on the active use of them in pedagogical activities is covered by innovative activity, innovative approach to pedagogical activity, justification of innovative ideas and effective implementation of them in

practice, awareness of pedagogical innovations created in foreign countries and the Republic.

V.A.Slastenin considers innovation to be a set of purposeful, directed processes aimed at innovating, spreading and using. Any innovation, according to the author, aims to meet the needs and stimulate the aspirations of social entities with the help of new tools. In any innovation, the concepts of “new”, “novelty” are important.[9]

The novelty, which is introduced into various attitudes and processes, is manifested in the way of content-private, subjective, local and conditional ideas. Private innovation takes the view of changing, updating one of the elements belonging to the attitude, object or process. Subjective novelty expresses the need to renew the self of a given object. Local innovation serves to describe the practical significance of the innovation being introduced for a separately acquired object.[10]

R.N.Yusufbekova focuses on the consideration of innovation from a pedagogical point of view. In particular, it is argued that pedagogical innovation is a state previously unknown, not recorded by the author in the process of education and upbringing, or the changing content of the pedagogical phenomenon leading to the result.[3]

Interest in applying innovative technologies and interactive methods to the educational process is becoming more and more widespread. The use of such methods increases the effectiveness and effectiveness of education, forms in students the skill of thoughtful understanding of the content of the lesson. Innovative methods of education make it possible to use and activate the enormous educational power of students, to introduce competitive elements into the educational process.[11]

An activity is referred to as a Novation (update) if it has a short-term, holistic system nature that only serves to modify certain elements in the system. Go-to, when the activity is carried out on the basis of a certain conceptual approach, the result of which serves to develop a particular system or radically change it, it is called innovation (innovation).[12]

V.I.Zagvyazinsky admits that the concept of “new”, “novelty” represents not only a specific idea, but also an approach, method, and technology that has not yet been used in practice. But in this, the elements of the process consist of elements that are holistic or separately obtained: changing conditions and new ideas; specific goals aimed at assimilating the system or direction of activity; unconventional approaches; unusual initiatives; advanced work methods are referred to as Novation (update) if the activity is short-lived, holistic system in nature and only serves to modify certain elements in the system.[13]

When the activity is carried out on the basis of a certain conceptual approach, the result of which serves to develop a particular system or radically change it, it is called innovation (innovation). embodies the ideas of effective solution of educational and educational tasks in the situation.

Indeed, being considered a novelty – tool, it is in most cases a new method, methodology, technology, etc. manifest in appearance. In essence, there are certain differences between Novation and innovation.[14]

I.P.According to Podlasie, educational innovators lead to the following changes: a complete change in the pedagogical system; a change in educational jaraèn; a change in pedagogical theory; a change in teacher activity; an update in student (student) activity; a change in pedagogical technology; an update in educational content; a change in the form, methods and means of teaching; a change in educational system.[15]

Students of the faculties of military education should focus on the following in their professional activities, extensive use of innovative technologies in professional activities, extensive use of new modern methods and innovative technologies in the process of military training, education in the conduct of military training will consist of the same educational process (activity of the head of training) and the mastering process (student) [16]

Able to apply innovative-acquired new knowledge to the military sphere by students of the faculties of military education in real military actions, work on it regularly and convey to the younger generation the knowledge gained in military training.[17]

The model of the process of developing innovative thinking of students of the faculties of military education consists of goals, principles, approaches, pedagogical conditions, content, Form, tools, criteria and results. Professional self-determination, professional suitability, professional selection and training, independently relying on life experience, made it possible to creatively approach the solution of professional problems, to creatively perceive and create innovative technologies of teaching themselves, to reveal the essence and content of such important psychological categories as professional competence.[17]

The conclusion should be based on innovative, that is, innovation-based technologies, new thinking in order to introduce new management processes.” Together with the provision of knowledge from the sciences in the faculties of military education of higher educational institutions, we should engage in solving pressing scientific and technological problems and become participants in innovative processes..

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